

INVESTIGATIONS ON HYPONITRATES. PART II. METALLIC SALTS

BY K. G. NAIK, C. C. SHAH AND S. Z. PATEL

In Part I, sodium and potassium hyponitrates were described. A number of other salts of hyponitric acid ($\text{H}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$) namely, calcium, barium, strontium, lead, and cadmium hyponitrates were prepared and their properties studied. Zinc, copper and silver hyponitrates could not be prepared in a pure state.

All the insoluble metallic salts were prepared from aqueous solution of sodium hyponitrate by double decomposition. They are fairly stable and can be stocked for a long time without undergoing change.

Calcium hyponitrate is obtained as $\text{CaN}_2\text{O}_3, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Angeli and Angelico, (*Gazzetta*, 1900, 30, i, 593) obtained it as $\text{CaN}_2\text{O}_3, \frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and Angelico and Fanara (*Gazzetta*, 1901, 31, ii, 15) described it to be $\text{CaN}_2\text{O}_3, 3\frac{1}{4}\text{H}_2\text{O}$. We obtained the barium salt as BaN_2O_3 by adding barium chloride solution to an aqueous solution of sodium hyponitrate; however, Angelico and Fanara (*loc. cit.*) describe it as $\text{BaN}_2\text{O}_3, \text{H}_2\text{O}$. Strontium salt has the formula $\text{SrN}_2\text{O}_3, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, whereas Angeli and Angelico (*loc. cit.*) report it to be $\text{SrN}_2\text{O}_3, \text{H}_2\text{O}$; and Angeli and Fanara obtained it as $\text{SrN}_2\text{O}_3, 1\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (*Gazzetta*, 1901, 32, ii, 15). Cadmium hyponitrate, $\text{CdN}_2\text{O}_3, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and lead hyponitrate PbN_2O_3 , were obtained having the formula stated by previous investigators. The lead salt has light yellow colour; the other salts are white crystalline powders.

Silver hyponitrate has been described by previous workers (Angeli, *loc. cit.*, Angelico and Fanara, *loc. cit.*, and Angeli and Marchetti, *Atti R. Acad. Lincei*, 1908, 17, i, 695) as a very unstable compound, which decomposes spontaneously and readily changes from yellow to grey owing to rapid separation of metallic silver. All attempts to obtain silver hyponitrate in a pure state have so far failed. While precipitating this salt by mixing aqueous solutions of sodium hyponitrate and silver nitrate a grey coloured precipitate was actually obtained as described above. The estimation of nitric oxide evolved in the process and the analysis of the grey coloured residue (Ag and N_2O_3) determination show that the product obtained has probably the following composition: $\text{Ag}_2\text{O}.3\text{Ag}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$.

No hyponitrate of zinc or copper has been described by previous investigators. Both these salts are very unstable and their decomposition is somewhat similar to that of silver hyponitrate. When attempts were made to precipitate these salts they decomposed evolving nitric oxide. The precipitate of the zinc salt obtained as a white powder, has the composition $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2.\text{ZnN}_2\text{O}_3$.

The decomposition of copper hyponitrate is rather complicated. The precipitate obtained in presence of ordinary air has got a greenish blue colour and has the composition $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2.\text{CuN}_2\text{O}_3$; if the precipitation is carried out in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide, a dark red precipitate is obtained, which, on analysis, was found to have the composition $\text{Cu}_2\text{O}.\text{CuN}_2\text{O}_3$.

Action of Air, saturated Aqueous Vapour and Dry Carbon Dioxide.—Calcium, barium, strontium, lead and cadmium hyponitrates are very stable and can be kept in dry air

for a long time without undergoing any decomposition. When they are exposed to dry or moist air or dry carbon dioxide, there is practically no change in weight except in the case of water vapour, where there was a slight increase in weight. The barium salt is the least hygroscopic of these. All of them retain their crystalline structure, as seen under the microscope, even on exposure to air for seven days.

Action of Water.—These salts are fairly stable when treated with water which may be due to their insolubility. The lead salt, however, becomes white; partial hydrolysis seems to occur.

Action of Acids.—When these insoluble metallic hyponitrates are treated with acids of different dilutions, it is observed that the decomposition due to dilute acids is comparatively much less than that in the case of sodium and potassium salts. As the concentration of the acid is increased, increased quantities of nitric oxide are evolved in a given time. In the case of lead hyponitrate, the decomposition could be followed on account of the resulting change of colour, the lead salt losing its yellow colour with decomposition.

Oxidation by means of Potassium Permanganate.—The oxidation under conditions already described in Part I is similar to that observed in the case of sodium and potassium salts, resulting in the formation of nitrite to some extent, the major part of the hyponitrate being oxidised to nitrate.

Reduction.—On studying the reducing action of the reagents mentioned in Part I, the highest percentage of nitrogen reduced to ammonia was 2.50%.

Thermal decomposition.—The main course of decomposition herein may be represented as

(where, M = Ba, Sr, Pb or Cd). All the alkaline earth salts decompose at a temperature higher than 320°, nitric oxide being the main gaseous product evolved. The residue left after heating is found to be alkaline and shows the presence of some nitrite and traces of nitrate. Lead and cadmium salts decompose similarly, but no nitrite or nitrate can be detected in the solid residue. The pale yellow colour of the lead salt slowly changes to deep yellow at 105°, which subsequently changes to brown at 120° and the salt loses weight, nitric oxide being evolved. The cadmium salt becomes anhydrous at 105°, slowly turning brown at 150° and decomposing at 200° leaving a brownish black residue containing no nitrite or nitrate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation.—All these metallic insoluble salts were obtained as crystalline precipitates by adding a solution of the corresponding nitrate to a solution of sodium hyponitrate. The precipitate so obtained was washed with cold water, alcohol and ether and dried in a desiccator over calcium chloride.

ANALYSIS

Calcium hyponitrate :— Found : Ca, 21.42; H₂O, 40.25, N, 14.62.

Calculated for CaN₂O₃.4H₂O : Ca, 21.28; H₂O, 38.30; N, 14.90%

Barium hyponitrate :— Found : Ba, 64.13; N, 13.25.

Calculated for BaN₂O₃ : Ba, 64.31; N, 13.16%.

Strontium hyponitrate :—Found : Sr, 43.75 ; N, 13.94, H₂O, 17.81.
 Calculated for SrN₂O₃.2H₂O : Sr, 43.90 ; N, 14.03, H₂O, 18.03%.

Cadmium hyponitrate :—Found : Cd, 54.51 ; N, 13.47 ; H₂O, 9.16.
 Calculated for CdN₂O₃.H₂O : Cd, 54.43 ; N, 13.60 ; H₂O, 8.74%.

Lead hyponitrate :—Found : Pb, 73.17 ; N, 9.80.
 Calculated for PbN₂O₃ : Pb, 73.16, N, 9.89%.

TABLE I

Oxidation with potassium permanganate (in presence of H₂SO₄)

Salt.	KMnO ₄ (0.1N) soln. reqd. by 1 g. of salt.	Equiv. of O ₂ reqd.
CaN ₂ O ₃ .4H ₂ O	319.0 c.c.	6.01
BaN ₂ O ₃	282.7	6.03
SrN ₂ O ₃ .2H ₂ O	320.9	6.40
PbN ₂ O ₃	217.2	6.14
CdN ₂ O ₃ .H ₂ O	283.8	5.95

TABLE II

Decomposition by acids

Salt	Acid used for decomp.	Salt taken.	NO evolved at N.T.P.	N ₂ as NO in salt	N ₂ as NO with salt	N ₂ as nitrite after decompn.	N ₂ as nitrate after decompn.	N ₂ (total) of colms. 6, 7 & 8)	N ₂ calc. per formula
CaN ₂ O ₃ . 4H ₂ O	HCl	0.1116 g.	18.76 c.c.	10.51%	..	..	..	..	..
	H ₂ SO ₄	0.0750	12.60	10.50	10.50%	4.43%	0.37%	15.30%	14.90%
	AcOH	0.1000	16.80	10.50	..	..	..	..	..
BaN ₂ O ₃	HCl	0.0750	10.99	9.15	..	..	..	..	..
	H ₂ SO ₄	0.0650	9.52	9.16	9.15	4.30	..	13.45	13.15
	AcOH	0.1000	14.64	9.15	..	..	..	..	..
SrN ₂ O ₃ . 2H ₂ O	HCl	0.1049	17.10	10.18	..	..	..	..	..
	H ₂ SO ₄	0.110	17.60	10.01	10.12	4.00	..	14.12	14.03
	AcOH	0.0700	11.40	10.18	..	..	..	..	..
PbN ₂ O ₃	HCl	0.0800	7.94	6.28	..	..	..	..	..
	H ₂ SO ₄	0.1000	9.92	6.20	6.23	3.60	..	9.83	9.89
	AcOH	0.1000	9.94	6.21	..	..	..	..	..
CdN ₂ O ₃ . H ₂ O	HCl	0.0940	12.03	8.00	..	..	..	..	..
	H ₂ SO ₄	0.1000	12.80	8.00	8.03	5.60	..	13.63	13.60
	AcOH	0.0750	9.70	8.10	..	..	..	..	..

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
 THE COLLEGE, BARODA.

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